

Ocular Itching

pharmacyinfoline March 8, 2024 2 min read

degloved face picture

Ocular itching, also known as itchy eyes, is a common and irritating sensation that can have various causes. Here's a breakdown of what might be causing your itchy eyes and some potential remedies:

Causes of Ocular Itching:

- **Allergies:** This is a common culprit, especially during allergy season. Airborne allergens like pollen, dust mites, pet dander, and mold can trigger itchy, watery eyes.
- **Dry Eye:** Dry eye syndrome occurs when your eyes don't produce enough tears or tears evaporate too quickly. This can lead to irritation and itchiness.
- **Irritants:** Exposure to smoke, dust, fumes, strong chemicals (like chlorine in pools), or fragrances in cosmetics can irritate your eyes and cause itching.
- **Contact Lenses:** Overwearing contact lenses, using old or dirty lenses, or being sensitive to lens solution can irritate your eyes and cause itchiness.
- **Eye Conditions:** Certain eye conditions, such as blepharitis (inflammation of the eyelids), conjunctivitis (pink eye), or keratitis (inflammation of the cornea) can also cause itchy eyes.

Remedies for Ocular Itching:

- **Identify and Avoid Triggers:** If allergies are the cause, try to identify and avoid your triggers. This may involve taking allergy medication or using air purifiers.
- **Artificial Tears:** Artificial tears can help lubricate your eyes and relieve dryness-related itching.
- **Cold Compress:** Applying a cool compress to closed eyelids for a few minutes can reduce inflammation and soothe itchy eyes.
- **Avoid Eye Rubbing:** Rubbing your eyes can worsen irritation. Try blinking rapidly or flushing your eyes with sterile saline solution to relieve itchiness.
- **Proper Contact Lens Care:** Ensure you clean and store your contact lenses properly, and replace them according to your eye doctor's recommendations.
- **See a Doctor:** If your itchy eyes are severe, persistent, accompanied by other symptoms (like redness, discharge, or vision changes), or don't improve with home remedies, consult an ophthalmologist (eye doctor) to determine the cause and get proper treatment.

Additional Tips:

- Wash your hands frequently to avoid transferring allergens or irritants to your eyes.
- Consider using an air purifier at home, especially if you suffer from allergies.
- Take breaks from screens like computers and phones to reduce eye strain.
- Get enough sleep to promote overall eye health.

Remember, this information is intended for general knowledge and shouldn't replace consulting a medical professional for diagnosis and treatment. If your ocular itching is bothering you, it's best to see a doctor to determine the underlying cause and get the most effective solution.

Suggested readings:

[Ophthalmic Preparations formulation considerations](#)

[Dermatitis: Cosmetic Science](#)

[Myopia](#)

[Decongestant Nasal Sprays: The Ultimate Guide to Relief](#)

[Preterm birth](#)